

1 **Using the best scientific knowledge for the sustainable management of**
2 **estuaries and coastal seas**

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19
20 **Introduction**

21
22 Estuaries and coastal seas are facing multiple pressures worldwide,
23 coming from human activities, which result in habitats and biodiversity loss,
24 introduction of invasive species, input of different types of pollutants (i.e., organic
25 compounds, pharmaceuticals, microplastics, noise, light, etc.), overexploitation
26 of resources, and climate change, resulting in the impairment of the marine health
27 status (United Nations, 2021a, 2021b). This, in turn, compromises the capacity
28 of supplying ecosystem services and delivering human benefits (Grizzetti et al.,
29 2019). Among these direct anthropogenic effects, global change is greatly
30 modifying the structure and functioning of marine systems (IPCC, 2021). To adapt
31 to this situation, implementation of management measures, rooted in the best
32 available scientific knowledge, are needed. Identifying such measures requires,
33 among others, long-term monitoring based on the ecosystem-based approach
34 (Borja and Elliott, 2021). This process, from monitoring through to implementation
35 of management measures, should be done through international collaboration
36 (e.g., within the UN Decade of the Oceans, the Regional Seas Conventions, the
37 European Marine Strategy Framework Directive, etc.), with the participation of
38 multidisciplinary teams, using novel monitoring, analysis and assessment tools,
39 including multiple origin data sources, and moving towards open science (Borja
40 et al., 2024).

41 To contribute to achieving these objectives, we proposed to organize the
42 Estuarine and Coastal Sciences Association international conference (ECSA59)
43 in San Sebastián (Spain), from 5th to 8th September 2022. According to the above
44 it was entitled “Using the best scientific knowledge for the sustainable
45 management of estuaries and coastal seas”; and 657 contributions, orals and
46 posters, were received, distributed in 45 sessions. This Special Issue provides
47 examples from those sessions and summarizes the current state of knowledge in
48 15 articles, including the effects of natural variability in estuaries; changes in
49 biological elements in estuaries, lagoons and coasts; studying the impacts from
50 different human pressures (including aquaculture, litter, eutrophication or
51 infrastructures); bioinvasions; and the effects of restoration on estuarine and
52 coastal ecosystems and their biodiversity.

53

54 **Natural variability in estuaries and coasts**

55

56 Natural variability in marine systems produce changes which sometimes
57 can have major effects in the oceanographic patterns of estuaries and coasts, but
58 especially in enclosed systems, such as coastal lakes. This is the case presented
59 by Dominović et al. (2023) in Rogoznica Lake (Croatia), with important
60 deoxygenation and stratification events throughout a time-series of 27 years; it is
61 of note that this is driving the system towards a progressive degradation.

62 Other natural effects in estuaries, such as natural erosion or
63 sedimentation, together with human pressures, such as dam construction, have
64 been explored in the Nakdong estuary (South Korea) by Lee et al. (2023). These
65 authors determine the sedimentation processes in the estuary, the lagoonal
66 system and a zone around the barrier island system for the period 2015–2021.
67 This study has enabled the monitoring of changes and interactions of natural and
68 human-induced changes.

69 The essence of estuarine functioning is related to the patterns of
70 connectivity between the estuary and the adjacent sea and between the estuary
71 and its catchment. Consequently, some of the natural effects coming from the
72 catchment area can affect the biological elements in the estuaries and adjacent
73 coasts. Miró et al. (2023) studied the effects of freshet events on early life stages
74 of fish and macroinvertebrates in the highly turbid estuary of the Guadalquivir

75 River (Spain). Changes in the different types of freshet events (varying in
76 intensity, duration, and period of discharge) had strong effects by decreasing
77 salinity and oxygen concentration, with large scale and notable changes on the
78 abundance and distribution of aquatic fish and macroinvertebrates. The recovery
79 of physicochemical conditions was relatively rapid, but some pelagic species can
80 be flushed out of the estuary. In general, estuarine and benthic species, such as
81 gobies and other macroinvertebrates, coped better with freshets than pelagic
82 marine migrant species, such as anchovies. However, the estuary and its
83 estuarine organisms showed high resilience to environmental fluctuations, a
84 feature reflecting the euryoecious nature of those species and a central paradigm
85 of estuaries that the organisms can naturally tolerate and indeed thrive in widely
86 varying conditions (Elliott and Quintino 2007).

87

88 **Human pressures and their effects**

89

90 In addition to natural variability, anthropogenic pressures are altering
91 ecosystems and their functioning. Low dissolved oxygen events, due to estuarine
92 eutrophication, can have large scale changes in demersal fish. This has been
93 studied by Nodo et al. (2023) in the Sundays and Swartkops estuaries (South
94 Africa). Hypoxic conditions resulted in a decrease in fish species richness and
95 overall abundance in the Sundays Estuary, while low oxygen concentration
96 events in the Swartkops Estuary resulted in fish species richness declined, with
97 little effect on fish abundance.

98 Human activities inland are producing an increasing amount of litter
99 arriving in estuaries and coasts, and there has long been the demand for the
100 monitoring of this litter, especially the non-degradable plastics, linked to the
101 biological repercussions (Borja and Elliott, 2019). Hence, spatial models
102 assessing drivers of estuarine debris can be important tools to take management
103 decisions, as studied by Gacutan et al. (2024) across four estuaries of New South
104 Wales, Australia. These authors provide an overview of debris composition
105 (mostly plastics) and employ Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA)
106 alongside Stochastic Partial Differential Equation (SPDE) to produce three
107 models testing predictors of debris abundance.

108 The selection of adequate locations for human infrastructures needs
109 environmental impact studies, and an example is that of the Liquefied Natural
110 Gas terminal in Tongyeong (South Korea), to evaluate the impacts of the resulting
111 cold-water discharge (Park et al., 2023). These authors evaluated the impact of
112 different flow rates on surrounding seawaters, on the surface and bottom
113 seawater temperature within a 1 km radius from the discharge. A machine
114 learning-based model was trained to estimate the diffusion and dispersal area to
115 identify the optimal sites of the discharge to minimize the impact.

116 Other human pressures come from activities such as aquaculture, studied
117 by Purgar et al. (2023), in Mali Ston Bay in the Adriatic Sea. These authors use
118 *Vibrio* spp. abundance as a water quality indicator in monitoring fish farms. Since
119 vibriosis is the leading cause of disease-related fish mortality in aquaculture,
120 monitoring *Vibrio* spp. has advantages due to their large health and economic
121 implications. Despite this, environmental and microbial quality thresholds still
122 need to be set.

123 Other sources of pressure on marine ecosystems come from bioinvasions.
124 Rifi et al. (2023), investigated the invasion of blue crabs *Callinectes sapidus* and
125 *Portunus pelagicus* in Bizerte Lagoon (Tunisia). These crabs produce important
126 ecosystem impacts, with potential economic effects. Combining molecular
127 analysis, questionnaires, participatory monitoring and awareness campaigns,
128 these actions strongly contributed to improving the level of engagement of the
129 local community.

130 One of these invasive species, the blue crab *Callinectes sapidus*, was also
131 studied in the Ebro Delta (Spain) by Prado et al. (2024). The species has become
132 a major fishing target in the area, and these authors investigated the trophic role
133 and predatory interactions between it and native species, using a stable isotope
134 approach. The high trophic position of the blue crab was similar to that of other
135 native predators, and the results suggest that the crab preys on all available
136 benthic resources.

137 As a further example, the invasion of the round goby, *Neogobius*
138 *melanostomus*, has produced important changes in the Baltic Sea coastal food
139 web, as determined by Morkūnė et al. (2024). Available data on biomass and diet
140 changes were incorporated in the Ecopath with Ecosim model, which in turn
141 estimated non-available data. Flow changes were related to round goby

142 predation on the Blue mussel *Mytilus edulis*, as well as to its contribution to the
143 diet of piscivorous groups. The model presented also analysed changes in the
144 long-tailed duck, *Clangula hyemalis*, biomass and consumption and an increase
145 in its trophic level. The authors demonstrate the food web ability to maintain flows
146 within given input and retain stability under conditions of changes induced by an
147 invasive species.

148

149 **Conservation, protection and restoration**

150

151 Marine mammal stranding data are sufficiently valuable to provide
152 information on length-weight relationships and consumption rates in odontocetes
153 in the Mediterranean, as studied by Carlucci et al. (2024), for the period 1983-
154 2021. The prey consumption pattern showed a clear partitioning among the
155 investigated species, where the common bottlenose dolphin exploits neritic
156 demersal and pelagic fishes (e.g. eel fishes, sparids), the striped dolphin exploits
157 mesopelagic fishes and myctophids, and the Risso's dolphin was specialized on
158 bathyal cephalopods of the Histioteuthidae family.

159 As a further example of statistical and predictive techniques to analyse
160 environmental data as a precursor to management, a Random Forest machine
161 learning algorithm, combined with remote sensing, was used by Agate et al.
162 (2024) to explore the marsh extent in the largest coastal plain in the UK, the
163 Severn Estuary, using data time-series from 1985 to 2020. The analysis revealed
164 a significant increase in extent and widths, increasing the natural coastal
165 protection. This information can be useful in the coastal planning process,
166 allowing decision-makers to assess the sustainability of existing defenses fronted
167 by marshes, as well as allowing them to make informed decisions about the
168 location of restoration schemes. This is a good example of Nature-based
169 Solutions for coastal protection which at the same time has benefits for nature
170 conservation.

171 With further regard to ecosystem restoration, van den Hoven et al. (2023),
172 investigated how natural foreshores offer flood protection during dike breaches,
173 again as a nature-based restoration method. Using a physical scale model these
174 authors showed that the presence of a non-erodible foreshore reduces flood
175 damage in the hinterland.

176 As a further example of eco-engineering, it is of value to demonstrate that
177 in some cases restoration can contribute to substitute an invaded habitat. This
178 was the case of an oyster reef restoration in an intertidal mudflat invaded by
179 *Spartina alterniflora*, in the Bohai Bay (China), as determined by Fu et al. (2023).
180 The study has demonstrated that the created oyster reef might slightly reduce the
181 sediment potential methane (CH₄) production and enhance the sediment
182 potential nitrous oxide (N₂O) production.

183 In other cases, the restoration of coastal and estuarine nursery areas can
184 produce positive effects on the stock dynamics of fisheries species, as shown by
185 Gernez et al. (2023). These authors focused on assessing the effects of nursery
186 habitat restoration for four species of main fisheries of interest in the Eastern
187 English Channel: sole (*Solea solea*), plaice (*Pleuronectes platessa*), whiting
188 (*Merlangius merlangus*) and seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). It is notable that
189 surface area and quality of restoration enhanced both biomass and sustainable
190 catch levels for the four species.

191

192 **Conclusions**

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194 Contributions presented at ECSA59, and specifically these 15 papers,
195 emphasize that management requires monitoring and assessment, in which
196 innovative technologies play an important role, and the need for using machine
197 learning for filling data gaps. As a global conclusion of this ECSA59 conference,
198 it can be said that marine science is providing an increasing amount of data and
199 evidence, to make informed decisions in multiple areas of coastal and ocean
200 management, thereby contributing to a more sustainable development of
201 estuarine and coastal ecosystems. Restoration outcomes, the United Nations
202 Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (Waltham et al., 2020) and the newly
203 approved Nature Restoration Law in Europe (Hering et al., 2023) give hope to
204 the ocean, and therefore, to society.

205

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